

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 39

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 39

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 39:0 For the choir director, for †Jeduthun. A Psalm of David.</p>	<p>לְמִנְצַח לִידִיתוּן Psa. 39:1</p>
<p>Psa. 39:1 I said, “I will ^aguard my ways</p>	<p>[לְ] [יְדוּתוּן] מְזִמּוֹר לְדָוִד : 2</p>
<p>That I ^bmay not sin with my tongue;</p>	<p>אֲמַרְתִּי אֲשֶׁמְרָה דְרָכַי מִחַטּוֹא</p>
<p>I will guard ^amy mouth as with a muzzle</p>	<p>בְּלִשׁוֹנִי אֲשֶׁמְרָה לְפִי מִחֶסֶם</p>
<p>While the wicked are in my presence.”</p>	<p>בְּעַד רָשָׁע לִנְגֹדִי : 3 נֶאֱלַמְתִּי</p>
<p>² I was ^amute ¹and silent,</p>	<p>דוֹמְיָה הֶחְשִׁיתִי מְטוֹב וְכֹאֲבִי</p>
<p>I ²refrained <i>even</i> from good,</p>	<p>נֶעֱכָר : 4 חֶם-לְבָי אֶבְקַרְבִּי</p>
<p>And my ³sorrow grew worse.</p>	<p>בְּהִגִּינִי תִבְעַר-אַשׁ דְּבִרְתִּי</p>
<p>³ My ^aheart was hot within me,</p>	<p>בְּלִשׁוֹנִי : 5 הוֹדִיעֵנִי יְהוָה אֶקְצִי</p>
<p>While I was musing the fire</p>	<p>וּמִדַּת יָמַי מֵהָ-הִיא אֲדַעַה מֵהָ-</p>
<p>burned;</p>	<p>חָדַל אָנֹכִי : 6 תִּנְהַ טְפָחוֹת </p>
<p><i>Then</i> I spoke with my tongue:</p>	<p>נִתְתַּה יָמַי וְחִלְדֵי כְאֵין נִגְדָה</p>
<p>⁴ “LORD, make me to know ^amy end</p>	<p>אֵךְ כָּל-הֶבֶל כָּל-אָדָם נֹצֵב</p>
<p>And what is the extent of my days;</p>	<p>סָלָה : 7 אֵךְ-בְּצֵלָם אִתְּהִלְךָ-</p>
<p>Let me know how ^btransient I am.</p>	<p>אִישׁ אֵךְ-הֶבֶל יִהְיֶינּוּ יֹצֵבֵר</p>
<p>⁵ “Behold, You have made ^amy days</p>	<p>וְלֹא-יָדַע מִי-אִסְכָּם : 8 וְעַתָּה</p>
<p>as handbreadths,</p>	<p>מֵהָ-קִנְיֵיתִי אֲדַנִּי תוֹחֲלֵתִי לֶךְ</p>
<p>And my ^blifetime as nothing in</p>	<p>הִיא : 9 מִכָּל-פֶּשַׁעֵי הַצִּילָנִי</p>
<p>Your sight;</p>	<p>חֲרַפְתָּ נָבֵל אֶל-תְּשִׁימֵנִי : 10</p>
<p>Surely every man ¹at his best is ²a mere ^bbreath. ³Selah.</p>	<p>נֶאֱלַמְתִּי לֹא אֶפְתַּח-פִּי כִי</p>
<p>⁶ “Surely every man ^awalks about as ¹a phantom;</p>	<p>אֶתָּה עֹשִׂיתָ : 11 הָסֵר מֵעַלִּי</p>
<p>Surely they make an ^buproar for nothing;</p>	<p>נִגְעָה מִתְגַּרְתָּ יְדָךְ אָנֹכִי כְלִיתִי :</p>
<p>He ^aamasses <i>riches</i> and does not know who will gather them.</p>	<p>בְּתוֹכָתוֹת עַל-עוֹן אִסְרָתָּ 12</p>
<p>Psa. 39:7 “And now, Lord, for what do I wait?”</p>	

<p>My ^ahope is in You.</p> <p>8 “^aDeliver me from all my transgressions; Make me not the ^breproach of the foolish.</p> <p>9 “I have become ^amute, I do not open my mouth, Because it is ^bYou who have done <i>it</i>.</p> <p>10 “^aRemove Your plague from me; Because of ^bthe opposition of Your hand I am ¹perishing.</p> <p>11 “With ^areproofs You chasten a man for iniquity; You ^bconsume as a moth what is precious to him; Surely ^cevery man is a mere breath. Selah.</p> <p>Psa. 39:12 “^aHear my prayer, O LORD, and give ear to my cry; Do not be silent ^bat my tears; For I am ^ca stranger with You, A ^dsojourner like all my fathers.</p> <p>13 “^aTurn Your gaze away from me, that I may ¹smile <i>again</i> Before I depart and am no more.”</p>	<p>אִישׁ וַתִּמָּס כְּעָשׂ חַמּוּדוֹ אֶדָּךְ הֶבֶל כָּל-אָדָם סָלָה : 13 שְׁמַעָה- תִּכְלֹתַי וַיְהִי וְשִׁוְעָתִי הֶאֱזִינָה אֶל-דִּמְעָתִי אֶל-הֶחָרָשׁ כִּי גַר אָנֹכִי עַמּוּד הוֹשֵׁב כְּכֹל- אֲבוֹתַי : 14 הֲשַׁע מִמֶּנִּי וְאַבְלִיגָה בְּטָרִם אֵלֶיךָ וַאֲיַנְנֵנִי :</p>
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References

<p>Psalm 39:1 ^a1 Kin 2:4; 2 Kin 10:31; Ps 119:9 ^bJob 2:10; Ps 34:13; James 3:5-12 ^cPs 141:3; James 3:2</p> <p>Psalm 39:2 ¹Lit <i>with silence</i> ²Lit <i>kept silence</i> ³Lit <i>pain</i> ^aPs 38:13</p> <p>Psalm 39:3 ^aPs 32:4; Jer 20:9; Luke 24:32</p> <p>Psalm 39:4 ^aJob 6:11; Ps 90:12; 119:84 ^bPs 78:39; 103:14</p> <p>Psalm 39:5 ¹Lit <i>standing firm</i> ²Or <i>altogether vanity</i> ³<i>Selah</i> may mean: <i>Pause, Crescendo</i> or <i>Musical interlude</i> ^aPs 89:47 ^bPs 144:4 ^cJob 14:2; Ps 62:9; Eccl 6:12</p> <p>Psalm 39:6 ¹Lit <i>an image</i> ^a1 Cor 7:31; James 1:10, 11; 1 Pet 1:24 ^bPs 127:2; Eccl 5:17 ^cPs 49:10; Eccl 2:26; 5:14; Luke 12:20</p> <p>Psalm 39:7 ^aPs 38:15</p>	<p>Psalm 39:8 ^aPs 51:9, 14; 79:9 ^bPs 44:13; 79:4; 119:22</p> <p>Psalm 39:9 ^aPs 39:2 ^b2 Sam 16:10; Job 2:10</p> <p>Psalm 39:10 ¹Or <i>wasting away</i> ^aJob 9:34; 13:21 ^bPs 32:4</p> <p>Psalm 39:11 ^aEzek 5:15; 2 Pet 2:16 ^bJob 13:28; Ps 90:7; Is 50:9 ^cPs 39:5</p> <p>Psalm 39:12 ^aPs 102:1; 143:1 ^b2 Kin 20:5; Ps 56:8 ^cLev 25:23; 1 Chr 29:15; Ps 119:19; Heb 11:13; 1 Pet 2:11 ^dGen 47:9</p> <p>Psalm 39:13 ¹Or <i>become cheerful</i> ^aJob 7:19; 10:20, 21; 14:6; Ps 102:24</p>
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Targum

Psa. 39:1 For praise; concerning the guard of the sanctuary, according to Jeduthun. A Psalm of David. ² I said, I will keep my way from sinning by my tongue, I will keep a bridle for my mouth, while there is a wicked man before me. ³ I was dumb, I was quiet, I kept away from the words of Torah; because of this my pain contorts [me]. ⁴ My heart grew heated in my body; when I murmur, fire will burn; I spoke with my tongue. ⁵ Make known to me the way of my end; and the measure of my days, what they are; I would know when I will cease from the world. ⁶ Behold, you have ordained my days to be swift, and my body is as nothing before you. Truly, all are considered to be nothing, but all the righteous endure for eternal life. ⁷ Truly, in the image of the LORD man goes about; truly for nothing they are perplexed; he gathers and does not know why anyone gathers them. ⁸ And now, why have I hoped, O LORD? My waiting is for you. ⁹ From all my rebellions deliver me; do not put on me the shame of the fool. ¹⁰ I have become mute, and I will not open my mouth, for you have done it. ¹¹ Remove your plague from me; I am destroyed by the blow of your mighty hand. ¹² You punish a son of man with rebuke for sin; and you have dissolved his body like wool that has been nibbled away; truly every son of man is as nothing forever. ¹³ Receive my prayer, O LORD, and hear my supplication, and to my tears do not be silent; for I am like a foreigner with you, an alien like all my fathers. ¹⁴ Leave me alone, and I will depart, ere I go and exist no more.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Superscript

This Psalm conveys the dismal mood of a crushed man shrouded in the gloom of his failures and defeat. According to Rabbi Hirsch יְדֻתוֹן is not the name of a person. He compared the Hebrew word structure and noted that it is the same as Psalm 77. It is not easy to understand his relationship with David if this is a name. This name can be found in 1 Chronicles 16:41-42. It is not clear from this passage if Jeduthun was the choir director. Therefore, Hirsch believes that Jeduthun is not a name.

יְדֻתוֹן (ydeeton) root word means “hand” and in its form denotes the activity of the hand. It means the eternally constant Divine providence as demonstrated in the fate of individuals.

To Him Who grants strength to master the providences of the LORD's hand, a Psalm of David.

Verse one

David said he resolved to guard his conduct not to do anything that the LORD may object. Every word that David said was to glorify the LORD.

I thought I will care to my ways that I will not sin with my tongue (my words); I will be careful with what comes out of the mouth while the wicked are in my presence.

Verse two

David's silence was due to his having attained peace of mind. He suppressed every thought of good, this good fortune. This silence did not soothe David. His pain became all the greater for having kept silent.

Then I became silent as if I had been soothed; I kept silent regarding the good, but my pain was all the more grievous for it.

Verse three

David's silence agitated him to the point that he could not remain silent.

My heart grew hot within me; the fire kindled on my brooding – then I spoke with my tongue.

Verse four

David saw the unjust distribution of possessions in the world. This process made him contemplate the true purpose of human life. Was it just good fortune that some people have more than others? He wondered if material possessions had any bearing on a person's ultimate destination.

LORD make me recognize my goals and what the measure of my days is, for I wish to know the extent of my days.

Verse five

טַפְּחֹת (t'fachot) – can be translated as “handbreadths” as is done in the NASB. It means a “fit's breadth.” This word can also mean “span.” David acknowledged that human life was brief, especially when compared to the age of the Universe.

Behold, You may make my days a span, and my short-lived existence is as nothing before you; Certainly, every man at his best is a mere breath. Meditate on this verse.

Verse six

The purpose of human existence is to resemble the LORD as closely as possible. Every word and action a person takes should contribute to being spiritually and morally equivalent to what the LORD would say and do.

Surely every person should conduct themselves in likeness to the LORD; and it is only for vanity that they are in turmoil; he heaps up riches and does not know who will gather them in.

Verse seven

David said that since he gained an understanding of the world's ways, he no longer yearns for material possessions.

And now, what is it I wait for? My hope is in You.

Verse eight

This verse is a twofold plea. The first is David asking to receive all the chastisement that he believed would remove the temptation to sin against the LORD. The second is to let him retain his spiritual and moral fortitude even in the face of suffering. The suffering was intended to teach him right from wrong.

Deliver me from all my transgressions, and make me not the laughingstock among the degenerate.

Verse nine

I have become mute, I do not open my mouth because it is You who have done it.

Verse ten

David asked the LORD to spare him the fate intended to train and discipline him. He knew that he had to endure these sufferings; however, he prayed that the LORD remove these things,

Remove Your plague from me; I have wasted away from the blow of Your hand.

Verse eleven

It was not the desire of the LORD to let humans perish because of the punishments. Instead, the judgment of Gevurah was to train humans to better behavior.

You have chastised every human for iniquity with rebukes by letting that which was close to his heart be consumed as if by moths; therefore, there is futility in every human. Meditate on this verse.

Verse 12 & 13

David realized that his time on the Earth was short. He was to be prepared and trained to live in Heaven for eternity during his time here.

Therefore hear my prayer, O LORD, incline your ear to my cry; keep not silent at my tear, for I am a stranger here with You. A sojourner as all my fathers were.

Turn away from me so that I may recover before I go away and am here no more.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To Him Who grants strength to master the providences of the LORD's hand, a Psalm of David.

I thought I will care to my ways that I will not sin with my tongue (my words); I will be careful with what comes out of the mouth while the wicked are in my presence.

Then I became silent as if I had been soothed; I kept silent regarding the good, but my pain was all the more grievous for it.

My heart grew hot within me; the fire kindled on my brooding – then I spoke with my tongue.

LORD make me recognize my goals and what the measure of my days is, for I wish to know the extent of my days.

Behold, You may make my days a span, and my short-lived existence is as nothing before you; Certainly, every man at his best is a mere breath. Meditate on this verse.

Surely every person should conduct themselves in likeness to the LORD; and it is only for vanity that they are in turmoil; he heaps up riches and does not know who will gather them in.

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You have chastised every human for iniquity with rebukes by letting that which was close to his heart be consumed as if by moths; therefore, there is futility in every human. Meditate on this verse.

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Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

